

On the individualized PIDA tuning for the automatic control of neuromuscular blockade

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Abstract: In this work we investigate a patient-individualized tuning methodology for Proportional-Integral-Derivative-Acceleration (PIDA) controllers employed for the automatic administration of atracurium to regulate the neuromuscular blockade level during surgery. The rationale consists in exploiting the administration of an atracurium bolus, given during anesthesia induction, to identify for each patient the parameters of a third-order minimally parametrized parsimonious model. This latter is then exploited to tune a PIDA controller with a Generalized Haalman tuning methodology. The performance is then compared with that of a PIDA controller tuned with a fixed set of parameters.

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I. Introduction

Feedback control in clinical pharmacology, particularly for drug dosing, has garnered significant attention over the past decades. Automatic control systems that regulate the administration of anesthetics, such as those for total intravenous anesthesia (TIVA), aim to maintain stable levels of consciousness, analgesia, and muscle relaxation during surgery. These systems leverage real-time patient data to optimize drug infusion profiles, leading to more stable outcomes and reduced workloads for anesthesiologists.

In the realm of muscle relaxation, the neuromuscular blockade (NMB) is often crucial for facilitating surgical procedures. NMB levels are usually managed using non-depolarizing muscle relaxants like atracurium, which require precise control to avoid complications from either excessive or insufficient blockade.

In this work, we investigate a patient-specific tuning methodology for Proportional-Integral-Derivative-Acceleration (PIDA) controllers used in the automatic administration of atracurium. By exploiting the open-loop response obtained from the administration of an atracurium bolus during anesthesia induction (as required by the clinical protocol), we identify individualized parameters for a simplified third-order model. This model is then used to tune the PIDA controller using a Generalized Haalman approach. Our method is evaluated against a PIDA controller tuned with fixed parameters.

Figure 1: Proposed control loop for the administration of atracurium.

II. Material and methods

The proposed control loop is shown in Fig. 1, where $r(t)$ is the NMB level of the patient and $\bar{r}(t)$ is its set-point value which is set to 10% according to the clinical practice. The signal $e(t)$ is the control error and $u(t)$ is the infusion rate of atracurium. This latter is the control action, and it is bounded between 0 [mg/min] and 200 [mg/min].

At the beginning of anesthesia induction, a standard atracurium bolus of 500 [$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$] is administered. Then, after a predefined time of 20 [min] (equal to the average clinical effect time of atracurium) the PIDA controller is engaged by closing the switch on $e(t)$ to achieve and maintain $\bar{r}(t)$. The PIDA controller is implemented in the following form:

$$PIDA(s) = K_p \left(1 + \frac{1}{T_i s} + \frac{T_d s}{N s + 1} + \frac{T_a s^2}{\left(\frac{T_a s + 1}{M}\right)^2} \right) \quad (1)$$

where K_p is the proportional gain, T_i is the integral time constant, T_d is the derivative time constant and T_a is the acceleration time constant. The filters on the derivative and acceleration actions have been tuned by setting $M = N = 10$, as typical in industrial controllers. A conditional integration anti-windup method has also been implemented [1].

In this work, we employed the minimally parametrized parsimonious model proposed in [2] to describe the relationship between $u(t)$ and $r(t)$. It is composed by a Wiener structure. Its linear part is described by the following transfer function:

$$P(s) = \frac{C_e(s)}{U(s)} = \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3 a^3}{(s + \alpha k_1)(s + \alpha k_2)(s + \alpha k_3)} \quad (2)$$

where $k_1 = 1$, $k_2 = 4$ and $k_3 = 10$ are fixed parameters and α is a patient-dependent parameter. Its nonlinear part is described by the following Hill function:

$$r(t) = \frac{100 c_{50}^\gamma}{c_{50}^\gamma + c_e^\gamma(t)} \quad (3)$$

where $C_{50} = 3.2425$ [$\mu\text{g/ml}$] is fixed and γ is patient-dependent.

The patient-individualized PIDA tuning is obtained by applying the Generalized Haalman approach proposed in [3]. For each patient, the values of the patient-dependent model parameters are obtained from the open-loop bolus administration by applying the identification method proposed in [4]. Then, a linear third-order model is obtained by linearizing (3) around the point given by $r(t) = 10\%$ and the values of T_i , T_d and T_a are determined by cancelling all the poles of (2) by means of the controller zeros, as in [3]. Finally, a desired gain crossover frequency $\bar{\omega}_{gc}$ of the loop transfer function is imposed and the corresponding k_p is obtained by means of a simple numerical procedure (the value of k_p is iteratively incremented until $\bar{\omega}_{gc}$ is achieved). The value of 1.67 [rad/s] has been chosen for $\bar{\omega}_{gc}$ to obtain a good tradeoff between control performance and total variation of the control action as in [5]. For the sake of comparison, the same approach has been employed to tune a PIDA controller with fixed parameters by considering as model parameters the average values of the patient database proposed in [4].

III. Results and discussion

The performance of the PIDA controllers has been evaluated in simulation on the patient database proposed in [4]. The results obtained with the patient-individualized tuning are shown in Fig. 2 while those of the fixed tuning are shown in Fig. 3. From the figures it is possible to observe that both tunings provide satisfactory clinical performance. The patient-individualized approach provides a more aggressive control action which, however, do not provide any significant advantage in terms of control performance.

IV. Conclusions

In this work we analyze a patient-individualized tuning methodology for PIDA controllers. A simulation study on a database of virtual patients showed that this methodology does not bring any significant improvement in the control performance with respect to a PIDA tuned with a fixed set of parameters. This suggests that the potential advantages coming from the individualization of the controller parameters are lost when a linear controller is used to control a nonlinear process. Thus, future works in the context of NMB control involving the individualization of the controller parameters should focus on the development of nonlinear patient-individualized control solutions.

Figure 2: Simulation results obtained with the patient-individualized tuning.

Figure 3: Simulation results obtained with the fixed tuning.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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